

PUTHIRA SOGAM

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Abstract:

There are two types of puthra Sogam. One is no child. Another is child with disability or child died before parents. The effect of the fifth bhava by Rahu / Kethu is very important factor for this.

Key Words: 5th bhava, 9th Bhava, No Child, Child with Disease, Child with Disability

Introduction:

5th bhava is not only puthra sthana but also poorva punya sthana. If it is affected by malafic planets a child would born with disability or child got separation from its parents, child born with DNA disorder with autism / down's syndrome.

Rules Applied for this Research:

- 5th and 9th bhava affected and the 5th and 9th Lord got debilitated.
- 5th Lord Stands in 3/6/8/12 bhava
- 5th bhava is aspected by Mars/Saturn/Rahu/Kethu.
- 5th bhava is not aspected by Jupiter
- Jupiter stands in 3/6/8/12 bhava
- Saturn or Venus stands in 1/3/5/7/9 11th bhava from Rahu
- Sun or Venus stands in 1/3/5/7/9 11th bhava from Saturn

Example Horoscopes of Couple:

Relationship	Husband	Wife
Name	Senthilkumar	Mohanapriya
Date of Birth	01.10.1985	28.12.1988
Time of birth	10.30 am	7.25 pm
Place of birth	Chennai	Chennai

	MOON RAHU		
	HUSBAND RASI		
JUPITER (R)		VENUS MARS	
MANTHI	ASC SATURN	KETHU	SUN MERCURY

KETHU		JUPITER (R) SUN	MOON
	HUSBAND NAVAMSA		SATURN MERCURY
ASC	MANTHI		MARS VENUS RAHU

Planet	Standing Star	Standing Patham
Lagna	Jyeshta	1
Sun	Hastham	2
Moon	Aswathi	3
Mars	Pooram	2
Mercury	Hastham	4
Jupiter	Sravana	2
Venus	Pooram	2
Saturn	Visagam	4
Rahu	Bharani	2
Kethu	Swathi	2
Manthi	Pooradam	4

Dasa Balance: Kethu 2 Years – 6 Months 18 Days

MARS		JUPITER	
RAHU	WIFE RASI		ASC
			KETHU MOON
SATURN SUN MERCURY	MANTHI VENUS		

MARSS RAHU	WIFE NAVAMSA		
JUPITER (R)			ASC KETHU SUN MOON
MERCURY VENUS MANTHI			

Planet	Standing Star	Standing Patham
Lagna	Poosam	1
Sun	Pooradam	1
Moon	Pooram	1
Mars	Revathi	1
Mercury	Uthradam	1
Jupiter	Karthigai	2
Venus	Jyeshtha	1
Saturn	Moolam	4
Rahu	Sathayam	3
Kethu	Pooram	1
Manthi	Jyeshtha	1

Dasa Balance Venus – 17 Years – 6 Months -13 Days

- In husband's chart 5th Lord Jupiter was in retrograde. Mars aspected fifth bhava in 8th aspect. It was very danger.
- In wife's horoscope 9th Lord Jupiter was in retrograde. No Planet had seen 9th bhava.
- They got a baby girl on 14.10.2013 with autism and dumbness
- In husband's horoscope Manthi stands in Second bhava. It cut the speech of the child.
- Venus stands ninth bhava from Rahu is also the reason for puthira Sogam.
- In wifes Horoscope Saturn stands eleventh bhava from Rahu is the reason for puthra Sogam.

Conclusion:

Above rules proves the puthra Sogam and gives autism child for the couple. Now, the child is given speech therapy and shows some improvement.

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